

A Prototypical Implementation of an ISO-15118-Based Wireless Vehicle to Grid Communication for Authentication over Decoupled Technologies

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Abstract—The progress of the Wireless Power Transfer (WPT) in terms of standardization and products had their implication on the technologies used for the communication between Electric Vehicle (EV) and the Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment (EVSE). One of the most prominent Standards for this communication, the ISO IEC 15118, is in the process of standardizing a wireless means of EV-EVSE Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) communication, next to the conductive, Plug and Charge (PnC) Standard, based on the Power Line Communication (PLC). Yet adapting the concepts of PLC and PnC to the wireless communication poses a series of challenges. This paper analyses the challenges implicated by the wireless communication, and provides a proof of concept prototypical ISO-15118 based implementation that provides a mechanism for achieving EV-EVSE Pairing, next to the Association and Authentication. This prototype implements the wireless V2G communication for the conductive charging case, yet most of the components are applicable to the inductive charging.

Index Terms—EVSE, V2G, ISO-15118, IoT, Wireless Communication, Electric Vehicle, Charging Infrastructure

I. INTRODUCTION

Large amounts of the current charge points (mostly conductive) use Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) Tags to identify, authenticate, and authorize the user of the Electric Vehicle (EV) in front of the Charging station of Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment (EVSE). Other current possibilities rely on the EVSE communication with the Charge Point Operator (CPO) back end that sends a remote command to the EVSE allowing the EV and / or its user to access the charging services [9]. This way EV-users can use any smart phone based Application of their E-Mobility Provider (EMP) or their Car Manufacturer (OEM), that retrieves the suitable CPO and send the remote command on their behalf. The other approach relies on the direct communication between the Electric Vehicle

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(EV) and the EVSE, as proposed in [7]. Further, when EV and EVSE have IP connectivity enabled, they can be seen as Internet of Things (IoT), that are able to communicate directly with each other over IP. This is the approach followed by the ISO-15118 standard, (and is the basis of the solution developed here). Once the EV is plugged to the EVSE, the Vehicle to Grid (V2G) High Level Communication (HLC) starts. This allows among other to negotiate the charging parameters and to authenticate and authorize the EV and the user using more secure cryptographic certificates in the Plug and Charge (PnC) case. Since many EVSEs lock their charge points (e.g. for vandalism protection) the standard Plug and Charge option often needs the involvement of the EV users to use the RFID tag (or other external identification means) to gain access to the charge point. Beside the discomfort, this user involvement is often error prone as the experiences in many cases have shown. Moreover, for inductive charging technologies, the use of RFID might be feasible for stationary charging, but certainly is less feasible for the dynamic charging while driving. Finally, the way RFID is currently used at the EVSEs is limited to the bare ID, and does not incorporate additional information (e.g. EMP-, CPO-, Booking-, OEM-service information) which poses security concerns and further challenges regarding data ownership for complex use cases, such as car sharing. The standardization bodies recognized these shortcomings and started working on a wireless extension for the ISO-15118, as a candidate to overcome these shortcomings and to offer more possibilities regarding functionality, reliability, and comfort of use. Nonetheless, unlike the wired case (PnC), where the communication is rather point-to-point, the wireless communication is point to multipoint. Thus, an additional Pairing mechanism is needed to make sure that the EV, which is (wirelessly) communicating to the EVSE, is in fact the exact one plugged at the Charge point or driving over the coil in case of Wireless Power Transfer (WPT). This paper describes the implementation of the ISO-15118 based wireless V2G that provides these functionalities while maintaining confidentiality, authenticity and integrity of the communication. This prototype implements the wireless V2G communication

for the conductive charging case, yet most of the components are applicable to the inductive charging.

The paper is organized as follows: first, a brief introduction to the ISO-15118 protocol suite is given, followed by a short discussion on the impact of the wireless link on the V2G communication identifying the related challenges. Next, a high level description of a solution that helps overcome these challenges is presented, followed by a description of a prototypical implementation of this solution. The paper concludes with a short discussion of the results of the prototype implementation.

II. ISO 15118 PROTOCOL SUITE

Fig. 1: ISO-15118 Protocol stack for PLC [2]

The ISO-15118 suite defines in its different parts the protocol stack for the Vehicle to Grid (V2G) communication. Throughout the different parts the ISO-15118 defines the entities of the V2G communication as follows:

- Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment (EVSE),
- Supply Equipment Communication Controller (SECC),
- Electric Vehicle Communication Controller (EVCC) of the respective Electric Vehicle (EV).

The V2G communication between these entities has the purpose of satisfying the use cases of the different actors (Users, EV- Manufacturer, Grid Operator E-Mobility Provider ...etc) which are defined in ISO 15118-1 [1]. The V2G stack is defined following the ISO/OSI layered architecture. From the Physical and Data Link Layers point of view the standard differentiate between two technologies: i) the Power

Line Communication (PLC) defined in ISO 15118-3 [3] of the standard, and ii) the WiFi technology, namely IEEE 802.11n, defined in ISO15118-8 [5]. The ISO/OSI layers 3 to 7 are defined in the ISO 15118-2 [2]. In its current published version, it bases its considerations on the PLC technology as shown in figure 1. On the Application Layer, it defines the SECC Discovery Protocol (SDP) and the High Level Communication (HLC) Messages of the V2G - Communication Interface (V2G-CI). The Presentation Layer defines the encoding of the HLC Messages to use Efficient XML Interchange (EXI) as specified in [14]. The Session Layer defines the Vehicle to Grid Transfer Protocol (V2GTP) that enclose the EXI encoded HLC Messages as well as the SDP Messages. On the Transport Layer, UDP is used for SDP Messages, and TCP / TLS are used for the HLC Messages. The Network Layer defines IPv6 over SLAAC [12] (or DHCPv6). Note that the HLC Messages are exchanged between the EVCC and the SECC and the ISO 15118 does not explicitly define the Interface between the SECC and the EVSE. The ISO 15118-3 differentiate between low level communication following the HomePlug Green PHY specification [3], and the HLC defined in [2]. The low-level communication includes a matching process where the EV and the EVSE use a kind of a modulation - simply toggling - between different states, called BCB toggling, before notifying the upper layers (IP-layer) of the respective link state.

With the PLC Technology, the IP connectivity is reached when the EV is plugged to the EVSE, which inherently means a tight coupling of the EVSE and the SECC.

Finally, ISO 15118-4 defines the conformance tests for ISO 15118-2. ISO 15118-5 will define the conformance tests of the ISO 15118-3.

III. WIRELESS COMMUNICATION AND THE ISO-15118

In earlier standardization phases, the wireless communication was considered separately. In analogy to ISO-15118-1 for the PLC case, the general information and uses-cases definition for the wireless case where defined in ISO 15118-6 [4]. The ISO 15118-9, which is still a draft at this point, shall contain the conformance tests for the wireless case. The draft ISO 15118-7 was supposed to be the analog of ISO 15118-2 containing the network and application protocol definitions for the wireless case.

In the course of the standardization, ISO 15118-6 was merged into ISO 15118-1 in its 2019 International Standard (IS) version. ISO 15118-7 is supposed to be merged with ISO 15118-2.

The wireless communication between the EV / EVCC, SECC, and the EVSE is depicted in Figure 2. Each EVSE can be connected to one SECC only, where the SECC can be connected to many EVSEs. Also for the wireless case the Standard does not define the EVSE-SECC interface. The EVCC is able to communicate with the SECC over the wireless link. In its turn the SECC would be communicating with many EV / EVCCs.

Unlike in the wired case (Plug and Charge), where the communication is rather point-to-point, the wireless communica-

Fig. 2: Wireless V2G [4]

tion is point to multipoint which creates several challenges for the communication integrity, confidentiality and authenticity [6].

The main difference between the wireless V2G and the PLC V2G is that in the PLC case, the communication starts when the car is plugged, and the communication partner (EVCC and SECC) are unambiguously identifiable. Furthermore, the SECC knows exactly at which EVSE the EV is plugged.

Where as in the wireless V2G, this is not true, and the wireless V2G protocol needs to define the necessary means to ensure unambiguity, confidentiality, mutual integrity and authenticity.

For this purpose, the standard defines three phases before the V2G communication starts: Discovery, Association and Pairing. The Discovery is the phase in which EV detects the available SECCs in its wireless communication range. The Association is defined as the process of establishment of wireless communication between SECC and EVCC. Pairing is the process by which a vehicle is correlated with the unique EVSE at which it is located and from which the power will be transferred either through a cable or through wireless technology. This ensures that the EV, which is (wirelessly) communicating to the SECC is in fact the exact one plugged at the EVSE or driving over the coil in case of WPT.

For the wireless case, the technology for Matching and the IP Connectivity are decoupled, and the IP Link can be established long before a matching process is even possible. Thus, additional messages are needed for coordinating the Physical sensing of the respective EV-EVSE matching on one hand with the EVCC-SECC V2G communication on the other hand. In its current version, ISO 15118-2 does not contain any means of coordinating the Paring messages over decoupled technologies between SECC and EVCC on one hand and SECC, EVSE and EV on the other hand. Next section proposes a solution for achieving this coordination with some additional messages.

IV. PROPOSED SOLUTION

When the EV is in the range of the Automatic Wireless Charging (AWC) network, it detects the different SECC and their respective EVSEIDs. Then the EV can chooses on

SECC to connect to (automatically or manually over an EV-HMI), and associates with it. In the background, the SDP allows discovering the endpoint parameter and the EV is able to authenticate the SECC and starts an encrypted TLS and TCP communication with the HLC messages. Therein at some point, the EV sends its public Key to the SECC, which in its turn generates a Challenge and sends it to the EVCC. Upon reception, the EVCC signs the Challenge and sends an Authentication-Request Message to the SECC. Which then is able to know whether the EV is authenticated (The authorization can be done either locally or by means of a Secondary Actor (SA) such as a CPO).

Fig. 3: Proposed Solution for Wireless V2G

The EV then parks and plugs to an EVSE, and start the Pairing mechanism. On successful Pairing, the EV can negotiate the charging parameters, sends a Power-Delivery Request, and is then granted access to charging.

Figure 3 shows how Pairing is done after the SDP and Association phases. EVCC asks SECC the authorization to start a Pairing sequence. After a positive answer from SECC Pairing starts. EV starts the sequence of B-State, C-State, B-State toggle (referring to the different vehicle states from IEC-61851) [11]. The EVSE that detects the sequence of toggles informs SECC of the Pairing toggles detection. SECC informs EVCC of the correct toggles reception. This procedure can be repeated as long as the EV needs to ensure that the Pairing is unambiguously successful. Once paired with the EVSE, the EVCC can continue the HLC communication with a Power Delivery Request.

The additional messages for Pairing have been chosen to be a separate type of V2GTP messages. This way the EVCC and SECC can leverage the TCP/TLS connection already established on one hand, are able to coordinate the decoupled technologies for communication and power transfer on the other hand. The following section describes the prototypical implementation of the wireless authentication solution.

V. PROTOTYPE IMPLEMENTATION

Figure 4 shows the actual component implemented for the prototype solution.

As stated before, the prototype implementation of the wireless V2G solution presented here, is based on the conductive charging. This is why figure 4 shows a IEC 62196-Type-2 [13] plug on the EV-Emulator side and socket on the EVSE side. In this case, the EVCC and the SECC can start the wireless communication long before the EV has plugged in the EVSE. When the EV is plugged to the EVSE, the pairing described in figure 3 can start. As figure 4 depicts, the EVSE and the SECC are enclosed in the same box for simplicity of the implemented prototype, but does not have to be the case, since the SECC can be connected to many EVSEs. The prototype implementation is built modularly, allowing easy adaptation to different technologies and setup scenarios. This way, for wireless power transfer technology, merely the parts related to that technology need to be replaced. Also setup of the prototype in an actual EV, simply require the EV and the EVCC controller to implement the EV-Emulator-EVCC-Controller interface. The following sections will give more insights on the different modules and components of the prototype implementation.

A. Hardware

Figure 5 summarizes the hardware setup of the different components implemented in the prototype solution, which are described in the following sections. The EVCC and SECC are able to wirelessly communicate with each other, which can happen as soon the EVCC is in the range of the wireless network spanned by the SECC (AWC-Network). Later, when the EV is plugged into the EVSE a lower-level communication between the EV (for the prototype EV-Emulator) and EVSE starts (BCB-toggling). To adapt the prototype e.g. to WPT, the EV (or EV-Emulator) and the EVSE (or EVSE-Emulator) need to be replaced by the respective technologies and they

have to implement the interface to the EVCC-Controller and EVSE-Controller respectively.

1) *EVCC*: This prototypical implementation refers to the conductive charging that uses the IEC-62196 Type-2 Connector Plug [13]. The EVCC consists of the following components:

a) *EV-Emulator*: is connected to an IEC-62196 Type-2 plug, and is built up by off the shelf microcontroller (Atmel ATMEGA16p) and circuit elements for implementing the IEC-61851 functionalities [11] necessary for the Pairing, which is done by doing some toggling pattern on the wire, based on ISO-15118-3 [3] (setting the states of the control and proximity pilot). Furthermore the EV-Emulator implements a UART interface to the EV-Controller, for sending information about the low-level state of the connected EVSE, and for receiving and executing respective commands (start Pairing, start charging ...etc.).

b) *EV-Controller*: is a Raspberry 3 device equipped with a WLAN module (802.11n) for discovering the different SECCs in the neighborhood, and reading out there Vendor Specific Elements (VSE) on the ISO-Layer 2 containing their EVSEID according to ISO-15118-8 [5].

2) *EVSE*: consists of the following components:

a) *EVSE-Emulator*: its hardware is based on the OpenEVSE [8], connected to a IEC-62196 Socket [13]. Its firmware allows us to control and access the lower level functionalities of the EVSE according to the IEC-61851, which makes it the counter part of the EV-Emulator for reading the toggling on the wire. It implements a UART interface to the Charge Point Manager.

b) *Charge Point Manager (CPM)*: Is a Raspberry 3 device connected with the EVSE-Emulator over USB, and implements the higher level messages of the Pairing process. The CPM reads the toggles on the wire from the EVSE-Emulator over the UART, and communicates them to the SECC, that in his turn tracks which EVSE has detected the respective EV.

3) *SECC*: is a Raspberry 3 device equipped with a WLAN module, which operates in the Access Point (AP) Mode and spans an Automatic Wireless Charging (AWC) network, and includes its EVSEID in its VSE.

B. Software

The functionalities of the Prototype implementation of the ISO-15118 based wireless authentication cover all the layers of the ISO/OSI stack. An overview of the functionalities and components is depicted in Figure 6.

The High Level Communication (HLC) can start after Discovery and Association. HLC is the bidirectional digital communication using protocol and messages specified in ISO/IEC 15118-2 IS. These include the Protocol Handshake using the Vehicle to Grid Transfer Protocol (V2GTP), over the Efficient XML Interchange (EXI) format [14], and the HLC messages such as Authentication-request/Response, Session-Setup- Request/Response Charge-Parameter-Discovery- Request/Response etc. The EVCC-Controller and the SECC-Controller based their HLC implementation on the OpenV2G

(a) EVCC

(b) EVSE and SECC

Fig. 4: Lab-setup for the prototype implementation of the wireless V2G

Fig. 5: Hardware components

Fig. 6: Software stack

library [10]. Next sections explain the software functionalities implemented by the respective component.

1) *EVCC*: The main software functionalities of the EVCC reside in the EVCC-Controller. It associates with a SECC using IPv6 Stateless auto-configuration [12]. It implements a SECC Discovery Protocol (SDP) Client to get the SECC settings and endpoint parameters over UDP-Multicast. Using these parameters the EV-controller performs a TLS handshake with the SECC by verifying the Root-V2G certificate, then its state Machines start the HLC-Communication by implement-

ing the client side of the ISO-15118-2. This is an Efficient XML Interchange (EXI) encoded communication, encapsulated in the Vehicle to Grid Transfer Protocol (V2GTP). When in Pairing state, the EV-Controller, sends the toggles through the EV-Emulator over the UART interface.

2) *EVSE*: As stated before the ISO 15118 does not specify the EVSE-SECC interface. In this prototype implementation, the messages between SECC and EVSE are exchanged over a modular interface, that is based on Linux IPC. This can easily be wrapped by any TCP/IP Protocol, or any other possibilities of communication (UART, Bus, wireless, ...etc.). This communication is done by the logical component of the EVSE-Controller (as shown in figure 5) following a Finite State Machine (FSM) design, and implementing the UART interface to the Open-EVSE [8] based EVSE-Emulator.

3) *SECC*: The SECC implementation is by far the more complex one, since the SECC communicates to many EVSEs on one hand and acts as an Access Point for the Automatic Wireless Charging (AWC) network, and thus communicating to many EVCCs on the other hand. In addition it acts as a server for the HLC-Messages for all the EVCCs. It listens on the Multicast group and implements the SECC Discovery Protocol (SDP) Server. It also implements the Server side of the HLC Communication in coordination with the SECC Session Manager.

a) *SECC Session Manager (SSM)*: is the central logical component of the SECC where the other components are linked together. It tracks the different charging sessions of the different EVs and their respective EVSE, including their state. It interfaces with the SECC-Controller for the EV communication and with the EVSE-Controller for the charge point information retrieval and control.

Note that the SECC does not know directly when an EV is plugged to an EVSE (or when an EV is driving over a coil for the WPT case). Therefore, it needs this information simultaneously from the EVCC and the EVSE During the Pairing phase.

Using these components the overall setup is complete allowing the modular implementation of the solution depicted in figure 3 for an ISO 15118 based wireless V2G communication with Pairing over decoupled technologies.

VI. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This prototype implements the wireless V2G communication for the conductive charging case, yet most of the components are applicable to the inductive charging. This is especially true for the EVCC - SECC communication (Discovery and Association), and the HLC. Merely the EVSE and The EV parts has to be adapted to implement the correspondent standards for wireless power transfer, which will affect the Pairing (and fine positioning) part of the implementation.

This paper provided a prototypical implementation for wireless V2G for ISO-15118 based authentication. This implementation is based on the conductive charging, using an EV-Emulator, that has been tested on many commercial EVSEs for the EV part, and an EVSE based on the widely tested OpenEVSE hardware [8].

The developed solution improves the PnC use case enabling vandalism protection, by allowing the EVSE to lock their charge points until a wireless communication between the EVCC and the SECC occurs, in that case the SECC informs the EVSE to unlock the charge points that might be a candidate for a PnC communication and the EV user is able to seamlessly plug, to the charge point chosen, and then Pairing can start. This is done with more user comfort, since the user is not required to use any additional RFID card in front of the EVSE, or any other means (such as a smartphone app for charging).

Therein it proposes the addition of further V2GTP Messages for handling the Pairing, which has been seen a question of low level and not part of HLC communication for the wired case of the ISO-15118. That is why the choice of not using HLC, and keeping the Pairing messages on the V2GTP level was made.

Because of its modularity, the prototype provides a basis for implementing ISO-15118 wireless V2G Communication for Wireless Power Transfer (WPT).

Note that this approach does not depend on the high precision localization (e.g. GPS) to determine the proximity of the EV to a certain EVSE.

REFERENCES

- [1] ISO 15118-1:2013: Road vehicles – Vehicle-to-Grid Communication Interface – Part 1: General information and use-case definition
- [2] ISO 15118-2:2014: Road vehicles – Vehicle-to-Grid Communication Interface – Part 2: Network and application protocol requirements
- [3] ISO 15118-3:2015: Road vehicles – Vehicle to grid communication interface Part 3: Physical and data link layer requirements
- [4] ISO 15118-6:2015: Road vehicles – Vehicle to grid communication interface Part 6: General information and use-case definition for wireless communication
- [5] ISO 15118-8:2018: Road vehicles – Vehicle to grid communication interface – Part 8: Physical layer and data link layer requirements for wireless communication
- [6] El Sayed, N, Lan L L. I. N., Goa, F., and Shi, X. “eCo-FEV: efficient Co-operative infrastructure for Fully Electric Vehicle.” IEEE Transportation Electrification, April 2014
- [7] Cirimele, V., Diana, M., El Sayed, N., Freschi, F., Guglielmi, P., and Piccoli, G. (2014, December). An innovative next generation E-mobility infrastructure: The eCo-FEV project. In 2014 IEEE International Electric Vehicle Conference (IEVC) (pp. 1-7). IEEE.
- [8] OpenEVSE tool kit, <https://www.openevse.com/kits.html>
- [9] Open Charge Point Protocol, <https://www.openchargealliance.org/>
- [10] OpenV2G, <https://svn.code.sf.net/p/openv2g/code/trunk/>

- [11] IEC 61851-1: Electric Vehicle Conductive Charging System - Part 1:General Requirements. International Electrotechnical Commission, Geneva, Switzerland, IEC 2010, IEC TC-57.
- [12] RFC 4862: IPv6 stateless address autoconfiguration
- [13] IEC 62196-1:2014 Plugs, socket-outlets, vehicle connectors and vehicle inlets - Conductive charging of electric vehicles - Part 1: General requirements
- [14] W3C Recommendation - Efficient XML Interchange (EXI) Format 1.0 (Second Edition)